

AGRICULTURAL REFORM PROGRAMME

REGIONALISATION OPTIONS

Scenario Builder & Dashboards

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Scenario Builder and Dashboard Components

*Standard Outputs, Standard Labour Requirement and Livestock Units for the Gain, No Change and Loss businesses.

Regionalisation Scenario Builder

- **Defines** a new payment regime (regions, budgets and other mechanisms)
- **Calculates** payments per business for alternative regionalisation options using 2022 Single Application Form (SAF) population as a baseline.
- Calculates the change in payments from the 2022 baseline.
- **Presents charts of payments and change** against farm type, agricultural region and size (area) classes.
- **Maps the rates of payment and change in** payment per business.
- **Saves the payments data** for further characterisation – in the Dashboards

Example of region focused mapping of change in payments – Argyll & Bute

Dashboards

- Takes data from the Scenario Builder
- Present interactive visualisation of the data (PowerBI)
- Links the scenario data with baseline (change)
- Link scenario data with other characterisations to look at distributions

Assumptions and Fixed Elements

- Budgets – fixed as 2022 (£) value, using the total payments to the SAF population as supplied to Hutton from RPID in May 2023.
- Regions
 - Uses the existing three BPS regions
 - Option to split Region 1 is available using a grassland arable split (with TGRS in arable area).
 - No change in the mix of regions per business.
 - Uses the 2022 LFA areas per business.
- Livestock
 - Types and numbers used for Voluntary Coupled Support in 2022 are fixed (but could be changed if alternatives were seen as desirable).
 - SAF livestock types and numbers in hand.

Mechanisms available in designing scenarios

- **Number of regions**
 - Up to four future regions, any combination of Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) regions
- **Area per region**
 - Determined by the assigned BPS regions
- **Money per region**
 - Constrained to stay within the maximum budget but otherwise free to be assigned between regions to best meet scenario goals
 - Other budgets may be converted to fully area-based payments (flattened)
- **Less Favoured Area Support Scheme(LFASS)** – a scheme specifically to address issues of disadvantage.
- **Voluntary Coupled Support (VCS)** – schemes where payments are linked to production systems – typically particular types of livestock seen as foundational for wider systems (e.g. suckler cattle).
- **Capping** – sets a maximum payment per region, for all regions or per scheme (e.g. VCS), typically used to limit payments for the very largest businesses.
- **Frontloading** – a progressive payment that favours smaller businesses. Pays more (a multiplier of the rate for the region) for the first x hectares of a business (which may be a mix of region types). Can also apply to the first x animals in a VCS scheme.

Scenario Builder Outputs - Change

Scenario – 2 Region – No SUSSS

1. Gain, Loss and Net Change by Ag-Region

2. Gain, Loss and Net Change by Farm Type

Controls Change vs Baseline Total Values

Ag Regions

- Shetland
- Orkney
- Eileanan an Iar
- Highland
- NE Scotland
- Argyll & Bute
- Tayside
- East Central
- Fife
- Ayrshire
- Clyde Valley
- Lothian
- Dumfries & Galloway
- Scottish Borders

Farm Types

- Sp granivores
- Var granivores comb
- Sp dairy
- Sp Hort and Perm Crop
- Gen Field Crop
- Sp cereals
- Mixed Crops - Livestock
- Spec cattle rear and fatten
- Var graz livestock
- Sheep & cattle comb
- Graziers
- Sp sheep & Goats
- Non Classified

Size Class

- <50
- 50-100
- 100-150
- 150-200
- 200-250
- 250-500
- >500

Baseline Scheme Participation

- SUSSS
- LFASS
- BPS/Greening - R1
- BPS/Greening - R2
- BPS/Greening - R3
- SSBSSI
- SSBSSM

Draw Graph

4. Options to present by combinations of Ag Region, Farm Type, Size Class or scheme participation

Totals Counts Standard Outputs Standard Labour Requirement Livestock Units Map

Redistribution by Ag Region

Redistribution by Size Class

Redistribution by Farm Type

3. Gain, Loss and Net Change by Size Class

Scenario Builder Outputs - Maps

Scenario Builder

Controls Change vs Baseline Total Values

Ag Regions

Shetland Orkney Eileanan an Iar Highland
NE Scotland Argyll & Bute Tayside East Central Fife
Ayrshire Clyde Valley Lothian Dumfries & Galloway
Scottish Borders

Farm Types

Sp granivores Var granivores comb Sp dairy
Sp Hort and Perm Crop Gen Field Crop Sp cereals
Mixed Crops - Livestock Spec cattle rear and fatten
Var graz livestock Sheep & cattle comb Graziers
Sp sheep & Goats Non Classified

SizeClass

<50 50-100 100-150 150-200 200-250 250-500
>500

Baseline Scheme Participation

SUSSS LFASS BPS/Greening - R1 BPS/Greening - R2
BPS/Greening - R3 SSBSSI SSBSSM

Draw Map

3. Maps can be generated for any combination of Ag Region, Farm Type, Size Class or scheme participation

Totals Counts Standard Outputs Standard Labour Requirement Livestock Units Map

1. Maps can be generated in real time as part of the scenario building process – example here of **change** but can also be **payment rates per business**

2. Gains for Region 3, losses for Region 2 and neutral for Region 1. Very clear regional patterns but added value of within region variation.

Scenario Builder Outputs - Distributions

Scenario Builder

Controls Change vs Baseline Total Values

Ag Regions

- Shetland
- Orkney
- Eileanan an Iar
- Highland
- NE Scotland
- Argyll & Bute
- Tayside
- East Central
- Fife
- Ayrshire
- Clyde Valley
- Lothian
- Dumfries & Galloway
- Scottish Borders

Farm Types

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Baseline Scheme Participation

- SUSSS
- LFASS
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- SSBSSI
- SSBSSM

Draw Graph

1. Total payments and mix of sources for Ag Region, Farm Type and Size Class

Totals Map

Dashboard - Change

Scenario – 2 Region – No Upland Sheep (SUSSS)

1. Charts as in Scenario Builder but fully interactive – e.g. selection to focus, or individual data values readable.

2. Charts of change by Ag Region, Farm Type and Size Class

4. Simplified version of the distribution of change charts

5. Switches between scenarios

6. Redistribution totals, also used for Quality Control

Dashboard - Distributions

Scenario – 2 Region
– No Upland Sheep (SUSSS)

1. Changes in payments for all businesses using the value of the change in payment (£), rather than how much that equates as a percentage of the existing payments (relative change)

2. Highlights the total losses for all businesses that are losing >£10k, so that they can be investigated further.

3. Tables of net change for Ag Region, Size Class and Farm Type

5. Swap between value and percentage views

AgRegion	Net Change
Argyll & Bute	-490.96K
Ayrshire	-752.39K
Clyde Valley	-813.72K
Dumfries & Galloway	-1,826.05K
East Central	-117.63K
Eileanan an Iar	373.34K
Fife	-94.18K
Highland	5,061.90K
Lothian	-273.26K
NA	87.44K
NE Scotland	846.95K
Orkney	-229.67K
Scottish Borders	-1,520.44K
Shetland	-642.23K
Tayside	390.90K
Total	0.00K

Class	Net Change
0	-13.78K
<50	41.84K
50-100	-107.42K
100-150	-283.97K
150-200	-290.30K
200-250	-292.31K
250-500	-1,707.31K
>500	2,653.25K
Total	0.00K

Farm Type	Sum of change
	87.44K
General Field Crop	153.10K
Graziers	740.37K
Mixed Crop - Livestock	-137.11K
Non-Classified	-15.49K
Sheep and Cattle Comb	-1,266.19K
Sp. Cattle	-697.88K
Sp. Cereals	-66.39K
Sp. Dairying	-250.41K
Sp. Granivores	-79.26K
Sp. Hort and Perm Crop	-17.05K
Sp. Sheep	1,156.80K
V. Granivores Comb	-12.63K
V. Graz Livestock	404.70K
Total	0.00K

Percentage of Changes

Value of Changes

Scenario

- 2 Region (BPS+SUSSS Only)
- 2 Region Flat LFASS (BPS+SUSSS+LFASS)
- Flat LFASS(LFASS)
- No LFASS (P1+LFASS)
- No LFASS Fr Ld (P1+LFASS)

Distribution of Change in Payments (Count)

4. Alternative view - counts of all businesses for each change in payment class – note the size of no change class.

Dashboard - Characteristics

Assessing where the money ends up – against other phenomena

Scenario – 2 Region + SUSSS

Comparing area of LCA classes and the funds associated*

Interpretation – will the distribution deliver the outcomes sought better than present one does?

*Money per LCA (or other) class requires assumptions. Example generated from average funds per ha for each business across the BPS claimed land. Not where funds generated but where they could be spent.

Dashboard Characteristics (2)

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Further research in the RESAS Strategic Research Programme 2022-27, in the [Land Use Transformations](#) (C3-JHI-1) and [Land Reform](#) (E3-JHI-1) projects.

Land Use Transformations - [Storymaps Collection](#), with [Land Use Change Scenarios](#), [Adding Farm Structure to Land Use Change](#), [Peatlands and Payments](#), [Updating Peatland Condition Mapping](#), [Updating Land Capability for Agriculture](#) and [Climatic Water Balance in Scotland](#).

Website for [Agrometeorological Indicators](#) across the UK under current and future conditions.

The [Review of Land Ownership Data in Scotland](#).

Previous related analyses are from the Hutton Land Systems Research Team website - <https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/research/land-systems-research-team/>

The sets of slides and maps generated in Agriculture Policy analysis from 2010 onwards are available from - <https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/research/land-systems-research-team/cap-analysis/>

For woodland expansion analysis see - [online mapping](#) and [paper](#).

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